

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

Stas Gorelik (2026): Review of the Human Rights Center Viasna's 'List of political prisoners and persons convicted in political criminal cases' (published on Human Rights Center Viasna), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/4AF13886-95D9-497C-8E35-03F751E033F3>

Abstract

The list of Belarusian political prisoners and individuals convicted in politically motivated criminal cases is compiled and maintained by Viasna, the country's most authoritative human rights organization, founded in 1996 by Ales Bialiatski, recipient of the 2022 Nobel Peace Prize. The dataset contains almost 8000 individual records and covers cases beginning in the late 1990s, with the majority dating from the post-2020 period of intensified repression. The dataset is available for access and download (tabular data) through Viasna's website.

Licensed as Attribution and Share Alike: Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL) ("share-alike")

**Review of the ‘List of political prisoners and persons convicted in political criminal cases’
compiled by Humans Rights Center Viasna (Belarus)**

by Stas Gorelik

The list of Belarusian political prisoners and individuals convicted in politically motivated criminal cases is compiled and maintained by Viasna, the country’s most authoritative human rights organization, founded in 1996 by Ales Bialiatski, recipient of the 2022 Nobel Peace Prize.

The dataset contains almost 8000 individual records and covers cases beginning in the late 1990s, with the majority dating from the post-2020 period of intensified repression.

Not all individuals in the dataset are formally recognized as political prisoners. Viasna assigns a case status: most entries refer to current or former political prisoners, while others involve convictions under criminal articles frequently used in political persecution but without official recognition as political prisoners.

For each case, the dataset seeks to record the date of imprisonment, the charges brought against them, the facility where they are serving their sentence (or release status), and the judge(s) involved. This information is not consistently available for all entries, though. Moreover, the publicly accessible online list provides fewer details than the underlying CSV file.

In some cases, names and personal details are withheld because families fear that publicizing information may endanger detainees. As with any dataset on political imprisonment in an authoritarian context, these records are incomplete: some cases may be entirely undocumented, and families may request that information be withheld or removed.

Data access: <https://prisoners.spring96.org/en/list>.